

EVALUATION OF NON-PROPORTIONAL MULTI-AXIAL STRESS STATES IN DRIVE-TRAIN COMPONENTS RELATED TO CONTACTS

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Estimating the fatigue strength of multiaxially loaded components using current standards has shortcomings for certain stress conditions. Therefore, different methods to estimate the severity of non-proportionality of load cases are investigated. First, four integral-based calculation methods are analysed on a simple plane stress load case. Their spatial capabilities are then tested for contact on an example of a shaft-hub shrink fit model. Qualitative two of the four selected methods perform well for this type of loading. Consequently, the basis for subsequent quantitative fatigue analyses with experimental validation has been prepared.

Keywords: multi-axial fatigue, non-proportionality, stress state analysis, contact stresses evaluation

INTRODUCTION

In all areas of engineering, relevant standards and guidelines form the basis for the design of components and component contacts. Particularly in the field of drive technology, calculations of highly dynamic systems with complex stress conditions emerge. Although current standards and guidelines (e.g. FKM guideline [1] or DIN 743 [2]) provide calculation bases for shaft-hub connections, these only use simplified methods that abstract the complicated local stress situation. Both publications enable a local strength verification, often using additional calculation algorithms (e.g. FE method). In most cases, the correction factors derived here relate to the maximum occurring stress amplitudes or critical load spectra. In the field of drive technology in particular, however, there is a superposition of differently composed stress curves. The resulting effect of the non-proportional stresses on the multi-axiality has not yet been taken into account [1, 2]. Depending on the material and type of load, this can lead to a reduction in strength and thus reduce the lifespan of the analysed components, as shown by Sonsino et. al. [3] and Hassan and Kyriakides [4]

Based on these findings, adjustment formulae were developed by Itoh et. al. [5] and Fesich [6], which enable the implementation of a correction factor for multi-axiality in the calculation methods. The factor K' is described here as an adjusted parameter, which is based on the material parameter α and the degree of non-proportionality of the load f_{NP} . The parameters K and K' can be selected as strength parameters of the guidelines, equivalent stresses or equivalent strain, depending on the specific situation, Riess et. al. [7].

$$K' = (1 \pm \alpha f_{NP})K \quad (1)$$

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The sign in front of the relationship refers to the application in each case, as a safety factor $K < 1$ or a utilisation factor $K > 1$ is calculated depending on the application. Without the influence of the material (i.e. $\alpha=1$), a value range between 0 to 1 results for f_{NP} , whereby $f_{NP} = 0$ corresponds to a proportional load.

At this point it should be mentioned that the evaluation of non-proportionality always involves a transient stress state $\sigma(t)$. Thus, an independent temporal change of the stress components is possible, which can be described by the degree of non-proportionality.

There are various approaches for defining f_{NP} . One group uses the critical plane method. Well-known representatives of this group are Fesich [6], Kanazawa et. al. [8], Papuga [9] as well as Skibicki and Sempruch [10]. What they all have in common is that before this method can be used, the critical component cross-sections must be defined in order to determine a critical plane for this based on the stress transformation. For a discrete system, this means that for each element n and each time t , a complete rotation of the intersection plane over two Euler angles must be performed in order to determine the most critical value of f_{NP} , Susmel [11]

In order to reduce the calculation intensity, methods have been developed that directly take into account the temporal course of the stress tensor. For example, Chu et. al. [12] show for the plane case that an enclosing ellipse of the stress path in the σ - τ coordinate system can be used to describe the proportionality of the stress state. The non-proportionality factor f_{NP} is calculated according to Eq. (2) on the basis of the main axis ratio of the ellipse. The smaller of the two main axes in the numerator must always be selected with $h < w$. Here h defines the height and w the width of the ellipse.

$$f_{NP,chu} = h/w \tag{2}$$

Many other envelope shapes can be selected in this way to determine the non-proportionality, e.g. Chen et. al. [13] or [9]. However, the application of this method fails for three-dimensional stress tensors or requires significant adjustments, which is why no further attention is paid to them. Nevertheless, this idea forms the basis for further formulations of non-proportionality, which have been extended to the spatial stress case relevant for contacts. *Bishop* [14] and *Gaier* et. al. [15] use the area moment of inertia of the stress trajectory instead of an enclosing form in stress space. To account for any stress components, the resulting tensor of moments of inertia is treated in R^6 space. This is achieved by transforming the stress tensor from $\sigma(t) \rightarrow R^6$. The shear stresses are provided with a pre-factor $\sqrt{2}$ in order to achieve coordinate invariance. The reason for this lies in the symmetry of the stress tensor. In [14], *Bishop* describes a numerical algorithm to implement the calculation. With reference to [14], the following equations are given:

$$L = \sum_{k=1}^N L^k \tag{3}$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{1}{2L} \sum_{k=1}^N L^k (\mathbf{x}^{k+1} + \mathbf{x}^k) \tag{4}$$

$$I_{ij} = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{k=1}^N L^k [y_i^k y_j^k + y_i^{k+1} y_j^{k+1} + (y_i^k + y_i^{k+1})(y_j^k + y_j^{k+1})] \tag{5}$$

Where $L^k = \|\mathbf{x}^{k+1} - \mathbf{x}^k\|$, $\mathbf{x}^k = \mathbf{x}(t_k)$ describes the distance between two points and the mean value corrected stress component $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is used. The non-proportionality is determined as the ratio of the maximum eigenvalues of the inertia tensor. Thus, an eigenvalue along the first principal

axis a_1 can be determined for each time t . Similar to equation (6) the next smaller value along a_i can be determined.

$$a = \max_{t \in [a,b]} \{ \|a_1(t)\| \} \tag{6}$$

$$b = \max_{t \in [a,b]} \{ \|a_i(t)\| \}, i = 2 \dots 6 \tag{7}$$

$$f_{NP,bishop} = \frac{b}{a} \tag{8}$$

A variation of the presented approach is given by *Gaier* [15]. While the calculation still uses the R^6 space the definition of the evaluation values is changed.

$$I_{ii} = \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^6 S_j^2(t_k), i = 1 \dots 6 \tag{9}$$

$$I_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N S_i(t_k) \cdot S_j(t_k), i, j = 1 \dots 6, i \neq j \tag{10}$$

The determination of the non-proportionality factor is inverted in comparison to *Bishop* so that the following applies to the eigenvalue consideration:

$$f_{NP,gaier} = \sqrt{\frac{I_6}{I_5}} \tag{11}$$

A significantly different method is proposed by *Bolchoun* et. al.[16]. Here, the proportionality of the load is to be estimated on the basis of the correlation of the transient behaviour of the stress components. *Cor* describes the correlation coefficient between the two stress components. A correlation of 1 or -1 for σ_x and τ_{xy} would describe a proportional stress state. The formulation can be regarded as spatial, as the correlation is integrated over the angles θ and ψ and finally minimised over ξ . The angular limits of the integrals and the minimisation operator are to be equated with a spatial rotation, which seeks the weakest correlation of the normal and shear stress.

$$M = \min_{\xi \in [0,\pi]} \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \int_0^{2\pi} Cor^2(\sigma_x, \tau_{xy}) d\theta d\psi \tag{12}$$

$$f_{NP,bolchoun} = 1 - M \tag{13}$$

The last non-proportionality factor analysed here was formulated by *Itoh* et. al. [17]. Itoh describes the non-proportionality as the deviation of the maximum principal stress S_I at time t from the maximum amplitude of the principal stress $S_{I,max}$. The time at which the peak stress occurs is referred to as t_0 .

$$S_I(t) = |\mathbf{S}_I(t)| = \max[|\mathbf{S}_1(t)|, |\mathbf{S}_2(t)|, |\mathbf{S}_3(t)|] \tag{14}$$

$$S_{I,max}(t_0) = \max[S_I(t)] \tag{15}$$

The non-proportionality factor is then described as the curve integral of the absolute maximum principal stress $S_I(t)$ and the deviation of the resulting vector $\mathbf{e}_R$ from the initial vector $\mathbf{e}_I(t_0)$.

$$f_{NP,ito} = \frac{\pi}{2S_{I,max}L_{path}} \int_C |\mathbf{e}_I \times \mathbf{e}_R| \cdot S_I(t) ds \tag{16}$$

$$L_{path} = \int_C ds \quad (17)$$

The pre-factors $S_{I_{max}}$ and L_{path} are used for normalisation of the equation for the non-proportionality factor. $\frac{\pi}{2}$ normalises for the case that the absolute maximum principal stress describes an ideal circular path.

ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT STRESS STATES ON THE NON-PROPORTIONALITY FACTORS

In the following, the integral non-proportionality factors described above will be examined with regard to their behaviour under different stress states. For this purpose, a theoretical 2-component stress state according to equation (18) is used first.

$$\sigma(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_a \cdot \sin \omega_\sigma t + \sigma_m & \tau_a \cdot \sin(\omega_\tau t - \Delta\varphi) + \tau_m & 0 \\ \tau_a \cdot \sin(\omega_\tau t - \Delta\varphi) + \tau_m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$\Delta\varphi$ stands for the phase shift between normal and shear stress. For all variations, the influence of individual factors is analysed over a phase range of $\Delta\varphi = [0; \pi]$.

The factors analysed that influence non-proportionality can be divided into the Amplitude ratio V_a , frequency ratio V_f and mean stress ratio $R_{\sigma,\tau}$ (eg. FIGURE 1). For the simplest case, in which only one normal stress and one shear stress are present, the influencing factors are defined as follows:

$$V_a = \frac{\sigma_a}{\tau_a} \quad (19)$$

$$V_f = \frac{f_\sigma}{f_\tau} = \frac{\lambda_\tau}{\lambda_\sigma} \quad (20)$$

$$R_{\sigma,\tau} = \frac{\sigma_m \tau_m - \sigma_a \tau_a}{\sigma_m \tau_m + \sigma_a \tau_a} \quad (21)$$

FIGURE 1: Parameter definition of different parameters: $\Delta\varphi$ phase shift; $\lambda_{\sigma,\tau}$ wavelength; σ_a, τ_a stress amplitude; σ_m, τ_m mean stress

As a reference state to analyse each influence the following parameters are set: $V_a = 1; V_f = 1; R_\sigma = R_\tau = -1$. This allows for an initial test where only the phase shift is of importance for the non-proportionality. The given non-proportionality factors f_{NP} are shown in FIGURE 2.

FIGURE 2: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for the reference state $V_a = 1; V_f = 1; R_\sigma = R_\tau = -1$

It can be seen that all non-proportionality factors reach the maximum value at a phase shift of $\Delta\varphi = 90^\circ$. This is in line with the expectations found in the literature [6, 16, 17]. The maximum values are in the range of 0.7 to 1. *Bishop*, *Gaier* and *Itoh* show a linear increase in the non-proportionality factor at the beginning, while *Bolchoun's* behaviour is similar to a distribution function. *Bolchoun* underestimates the non-proportionality in the range up to $\Delta\varphi < \frac{\pi}{8}$ compared to the other factors. From $\Delta\varphi > \frac{\pi}{4}$ *Bolchoun* overestimates the non-proportionality. The non-linear behaviour of *Bolchoun* can be traced back to the quadratic consideration of the correlation coefficient. *Bolchoun* is the only factor to reach the maximum value of $f_{NP} = 1$ for the defined initial state. The reason why *Bishop* and *Gaier* do not reach the value of $f_{NP} = 1$ is the scaling of the shear stress components in the calculation, where the shear stresses have a stronger influence on the course of the stresses than the normal stress. This behaviour is described in more detail in [15].

Below, the individual influencing factors are adjusted in isolation from each other in order to be able to evaluate the individual influences. The variation of the individual components can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameter set for the analysis of the influencing factors

Parameter				
Amplitude ratio V_a	0.5	0.75	$\sqrt{2}$	$\sqrt{3}$
Frequency ratio V_f	0.25	0.5	0.75	1.25
Normal Stress ratio R_σ	-0.6	-0.33	0	0.2
Shear Stress ratio R_τ	-0.6	-0.33	0	0.2

Firstly, the influence of the amplitude ratio is analysed according to equation (19). The stress amplitude of the normal stress is varied with a constant shear stress amplitude. The variation results are shown in FIGURE 3. The initial state $V_a = 1$ is shown as grey graphs for the individual non-proportionality factors. In the case of Bishop, Gaier and Itoh, a change in the amplitude ratio leads to a scaling of the non-proportionality values obtained. The position of the maximum remains the same with a phase shift of $\Delta\varphi = 90^\circ$. By scaling the normal stress to $\sigma_a = \sqrt{2} \cdot \tau_a$, the non-proportionality factors according to *Bishop* and *Gaier* reach the maximum value of $f_{NP} = 1$. As mentioned for the initial state, this behaviour is related to the definition of the stress tensor in R^6 -space. As the amplitude ratio decreases, the curvature of the curve also decreases. Like *Bishop* and *Gaier*, *Itoh* shows a scaling of the non-proportionality factor with a change in the amplitude ratio. However, the progression over the phase shift is significantly more linear. If the amplitude ratio is increased above $\sqrt{2}$, the non-proportionality factor decreases. The normal stress outweighs the shear stress, so the tensor path is predominantly determined by the normal stress. Compared to the three variants mentioned, *Bolchoun* shows no change in non-proportionality with a changed stress ratio. This results from the definition of the correlation, which evaluates the relationship between the two stress functions independently of the amplitude.

FIGURE 3: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable amplitude ratios

As a second influencing factor, the frequency ratio is analysed according to equation (20). Here, the frequency of the normal stress is varied at a constant shear stress frequency. The variation results are shown in FIGURE 4. Compared to the amplitude ratio, there is a clear change in the course of the

non-proportionality. Not only does the magnitude of the non-proportionality factor change as a function of the phase shift, but also the position of the maximum non-proportionality. All factors show non-proportionality for the analysed stress states for all phase shifts. For the frequency ratio $V_f = 0.5$ there is a shift of 90° in the position of maximum non-proportionality compared to the initial state. No clear dependence of the maximum and minimum values of the non-proportionality factors achieved can be recognised. Only *Bolchoun* always reaches the value for certain phase shifts $f_{NP} = 1$ which corresponds to a zero correlation. It is also noticeable that discontinuities can be recognised for the non-proportionality factor according to *Itoh* for $V_f = 0.25$. This is due to the fact that the low frequency leads to an open main stress path, which causes problems in the numerical solution algorithm when integrating the boundary regions. This observation can also be seen without abrupt change for the frequency ratios $V_f = 0.75$ and $V_f = 1.25$. This problem can be solved by an extended stress curve in which the stress paths must be closed.

FIGURE 4: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable frequency ratios

In the following, the influence of the normal stress ratio R_σ according to Eq. (21) is analysed. Here, a mean stress is applied in addition to the cyclical stress curve of the normal stress. As for the amplitude ratio, the non-proportionality factor according to *Bolchoun* shows no dependence on the stress ratio. This can also be explained by the correlation definition. *Bishop* also shows no influence of the stress ratio on the non-proportionality. This is due to the correction of the stress paths by the mean stress component $\bar{x}$. This changes the position of the origin of the tensor path under consideration; in this case, the shift takes place exactly at the level of the mean stress. In comparison,

Gaier, who does not correct for the mean stress, shows a clear influence of the stress ratio. A non-proportionality is also determined in the two in-phase positions $\Delta\varphi = 0^\circ, 180^\circ$. As the stress ratio increases, the maximum of the non-proportionality for *Gaier* also increases until it flattens out between $R_\sigma = -0.33$ and $R_\sigma = 0$. A further increase in the stress ratio leads to a decreasing maximum non-proportionality, which approaches a constant non-proportionality over all phase shifts. The level of this constant depends on the level of the mean stress. *Itoh* also shows a dependence of the non-proportionality on the stress ratio. In contrast to the purely alternating stress, a mean stress in the in-phase position is also evaluated as non-proportionality in *Itoh*. In comparison to *Gaier*, *Itoh* no longer reaches the maximum value of the initial state. A strong increase in the mean stress also leads to a flat curve of the non-proportionality factor over the phase angle for *Itoh*.

FIGURE 5: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable normal mean stress ratios

Similar behaviour to the normal stress ratio R_σ can be observed for the shear stress ratio R_τ . The non-proportionality factors according to *Bishop* and *Bolchoun* show no change due to an inserted mean stress. *Gaier* and *Itoh* show a decrease in non-proportionality compared to the initial state. For both, the flattening of the curve is significantly faster than for the case of normal mean stress. It can also be observed that the values in in-phase positions are significantly lower than for the normal mean stress. The reason for this behaviour is the scaling of the shear stress in *Gaier* and the influence of the shear stress in the main stress system in *Itoh*.

FIGURE 6: Non-proportionality factors at different phase shifts for a variable shear mean stress ratios

To summarise the analysis of the influencing factors, it can be said that different dependencies of the stress state can be detected depending on the calculation method which is used to determine the non-proportionality. The most generally valid influence here is the frequency ratio V_f . The non-proportionality factor according to *Bolchoun* reacts most insensitively; due to the correlation definition, mean stresses and amplitude changes are disregarded here. As expected, for a constant frequency, the maximum non-proportionality for all factors occurs at a phase shift of 90° . Here, an amplitude ratio of $\sqrt{2}$ appears to lead to a maximum assessment of the damaging effect caused by non-proportional stress. This is mainly due to the scaling of the shear stresses around the analysed tensor space in the case of *Bishop* and *Gaier*. Only *Itoh* and *Gaier* reacted to an introduced mean stress in the simplest case, where both detected a non-proportionality for the in-phase positions. From a certain degree of the stress ratio, the maximum non-proportionality decreases, as the main component of the stress tensor is determined by the mean stress.

APPLICATION OF NON-PROPORTIONALITY FACTORS TO SHAFT-HUB PRESS-FITS

The non-proportionality factors analysed are now to be applied to an application in the drivetrain. The focus here is on individually or combined loaded shaft-hub press-fit connections. The interference fit introduces additional normal stress components in the stress tensor perpendicular to

the surface. This leads to a complex three-dimensional stress state within the shaft-hub connection, which represents the natural extension for analysing the influencing factors.

Three FE models were analysed to determine the stress tensors. One model of the press connection under pure torsional load, another under a rotating bending load and one under a combined rotating bending-torsional load. Due to the symmetry of the connection, one model is sufficient for the superimposed load to analyse the phase shift of the bending and torsional stress. To do this, only the evaluation position on the circumference needs to be adjusted, whereby $\Delta\varphi$ can be influenced here by the temporal occurrence of the bending stress at the evaluation position.

The models of the single loads only require an evaluation at one critical point, as no additional phase shift between normal and shear stress components can occur. In all models, the evaluation zone is located on the shaft side in the area of the hub edge. In order to exclude the singularity, the evaluation takes place a few nodes below the contact zone and axially inside the shaft.

The structure of the model is shown in FIGURE 7. Depending on the load, the bending moment M_B , the torque M_T or both loads are activated. The hub is fixed on the back. The FE mesh has a fractal-like structure at the contact edge, as this is where the greatest degree of damage is expected. The simulation sequence begins with the application of the pressure without active friction in order to reduce the shear stresses introduced. After applying the pressure as an interference fit, the friction is activated. A simple penalty algorithm is used for this. In an intermediate step, the initial bending moment is set for the rotating bending. This is important because the bending moments in the x and y directions are applied as opposing sine and cosine functions to represent the rotating bending effect. In the last step, the other loads (opposing bending component and torsion, if applicable) are applied. The loads correspond to the fatigue strengths from the respective tests [18].

After completion of the load cycles, the area marked in FIGURE 7 is continuously evaluated for the superimposed load. For the individual loads, only one point in the x - z -plane is analysed.

FIGURE 7: Finite-Element-Model of a shaft-hub press-fit

The evaluation initially includes an analysis of the stress state. For this purpose, the individual components are scaled to the Lamé pressure $p_L = 134$ MPa. The temporal progression of the stress component is shown in FIGURE 8 for the individual loads bending (a) and torsion (b), as well as for the superimposed load at 0° phase shift (c) and 90° phase shift (d). In addition, the course of the

stress components against each other (right) is shown in matrix form. Here, the course of the stress tensor can be analysed without scaled shear stresses for the individual components.

As already described above, the special feature of the contact stress states compared to the free surface is the occupancy of the tensor points, which occur both as cyclic stresses and as constant mean stresses in space. In general, normal mean stresses initially occur on the shaft surface in the vicinity of the hub edge after joining the shrink fit.

In addition, in the case of rotating bending, the cyclic parts characterise the stress state of this component according to the stress concentration (notch). The initial pressure increases on the bending compression side and relaxes on the opposite bending tension side. The shear stress component in the axial direction is caused by friction in the slip zone of the interference fit and its level depends on the existing coefficient of friction.

In the case of pure alternating torsion, the mounting stress in the normal direction remains unaffected. The stress state is characterised by two shear stress components: the shear stress on the shaft surface, which is comparable to contactless notches, and shear stress in the radial-tangential direction. Due to the slip condition, this shear stress does not exhibit a harmonic curve and is "cut off" in this contact area due to the slip. The height of the plateau depends on the coefficient of friction, which can differ several times from the initial value in this region due to the low surface damage.

In simplified terms, it can be concluded that the described stress states of the individual loads are also superimposed for the rotating bending and the alternating torsion (see FIGURE 8). However, additional alternating mechanisms occur which change the amplitude ratios. These cannot easily be described analytically and depend heavily on the geometric contact design. It can be stated that all components have an oscillating and mean-stress character. The type of load superposition results in a phase shift of the nominal loads over the circumference, as described in detail in [18]. This is also reflected in the local stress in the shear stress component.

The analysis initially shows that non-proportionality is also pronounced for individual loads, depending on the approach. With the exception of *Bolchoun*, low values between $f_{NP} = 0.07 \dots 0.21$ are calculated for pure rotating bending. *Bolchoun* calculates $f_{NP} = 0.99$ as the most damaging effect of the stress state.

In the case of pure torsion, the calculation is divided into two groups. While the approaches according to *Bolchoun* and *Gaier* predict the highest non-proportionality with an almost fully non-proportional stress state, the values according to *Itoh* and *Bishop* are $f_{NP} = 0.33 \dots 0.40$.

When superimposing rotating bending with alternating torsion, the loads are dependent on the circumferential position and thus the phase position. Here, the 90° phase position proves to be the most critical stress state. The calculations result in $f_{NP} = 0.56 \dots 1$. At 0° -phase shift *Itoh* and *Gaier* predict a non-zero non-proportionality of $f_{NP} = 0.41 \dots 0.43$. In contrast, *Bishop* and *Bolchoun* evaluate the stress state at the hub edge as proportional.

FIGURE 8: Transient stresses in shrink fits underneath the contact hub edge; a) rotating bending, b) alternating torsion, c) superposition of rotating bending and torsion at $\phi=0^\circ$, d) at $\phi=90^\circ$

TABLE 2: Results of non-proportionality factors of uniaxially and multiaxially loaded press fits

	Itoh	Bishop	Gaier	Bolchoun
Bending	0.18	0.07	0.21	0.99
Torsion	0.40	0.33	0.95	0.99
0° combined	0.43	0.07	0.41	0.04
90° combined	0.81	0.88	0.56	1.00

SUMMARY – OUTLOOK

The approaches presented here for calculating the non-proportionality of a transient stress state are of great interest for a simple strength assessment. An integration into one of the known strength analyses would enable an estimation of the durability of components without complex numerical investigation of the strength hypotheses. Previous studies on non-proportionality mainly relate to the low cycle fatigue strength and the plane stress state. An analysis of selected calculation approaches for non-proportionality factors (*Bishop*, *Gaier*, *Itoh*, *Bolchoun*) clearly show the influence of the amplitude and frequency ratios as well as the mean stresses on the degree of non-proportionality at different phase shifts of the normal and shear stresses. Qualitatively, all calculation methods show a similar tendency, but quantitatively there are large differences. For example, *Bolchoun* in particular shows major weaknesses in the calculation due to the correlation definition.

For components with contacts, however, analysing the two-dimensional stress state is not sufficient, as a spatial stress state exists at the interface due to the contact pressures applied. In practice, the non-proportional stress states are considered using notch factors, however these have to be determined experimentally by time consuming model tests. For this reason, the methods of non-proportionality factors were investigated in more detail using a shaft-hub-press fit typical of drive technology. Although *Itoh* shows clear numerical instabilities for frequency deviations, the non-proportionality estimation for the three-dimensional stress space appears to be the most plausible. *Bishop* seems to underestimate the non-proportionality as he does not consider the mean stress, especially for superimposed loading. In contrast, *Gaier* overestimates the influence of the mean contact stress for the load case of pure torsion. But it is not clear, if this effect is already included in the common mean stress consideration in the calculation standards.

To summarise, it can be seen that it is still difficult to assess non-proportionality without a strength verification with experimental validation. However, a qualitative assessment using numerical methods appears to make sense in order to check the robustness of existing calculation concepts. Further investigations with integration of the non-proportionality factors into a strength verification are being sought-after.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

- a_i ... principle axis of stress tensor
 b ... second axis of stress tensor
 e ... Eigenvector of stress tensor
 f ... frequency
 f_{NP} ... non-proportionality factor
 h ... height of enclosure ellipse
 s ... length between two points in stress space
 t ... time component
 w ... width of enclosure ellipse
 x ... stress component in R^6
 y ... stress component in R^6 without mean stress
 I ... inertia component
 K ... safety factor for multiaxial stress
 L ... length of the stress path
 M ... integrated correlation value
 R ... mean stress ratio
 S ... stress tensor/component
 α ... material hardening parameter
 σ ... normal stress
 τ ... shear stress
 φ ... phase shift
 θ, ψ, ξ ... coordinate angles

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